

Supporting Information

Moving Beyond Cyanoarene Thermally Activated Delayed Fluorescence Compounds as Photocatalysts: An Assessment of the Performance of a Pyrimidyl Sulfone Photocatalyst in Comparison to 4CzIPN

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Experimental Section

General Synthetic Procedures. The following starting materials were synthesised according to literature procedures: **4CzIPN**,¹ **2CzPN**,² **[Ru(bpy)₃](PF₆)₂**,³ **[Ir(dF(CF₃)ppy)₂(dtbbpy)]PF₆**,⁴ **[Cu(dap)₂]Cl**,⁵ **[Cu(dmp)(Xantphos)]PF₆**,⁶ **(bromoethynyl)benzene**,⁷ **1,3-dioxoisindolin-2-yl cyclohexanecarboxylate**,⁸ **Hantzsch ester**⁹ and ***N*-Cbz-proline**.¹⁰ All other reagents and solvents were obtained from commercial sources and used as received. Air-sensitive reactions were performed under a nitrogen atmosphere using Schlenk techniques, no special precautions were taken to exclude air or moisture during work-up and crystallisation. Anhydrous THF, DCM, toluene and acetonitrile were obtained from a MBraun SPS5 solvent purification system. Flash column chromatography was carried out using silica gel (Silia-P from Silicycle, 60 Å, 40-63 µm). Analytical thin-layer-chromatography (TLC) was performed with silica plates with aluminum backings (250 µm with F-254 indicator). TLC visualization was accomplished by 254/365 nm UV lamp. ¹H spectra were recorded on a Bruker Advance spectrometer (400 or 500 MHz for ¹H). The following abbreviations have been used for multiplicity assignments: “s” for singlet, “d” for doublet, “t” for triplet, “q” for quartet, “m” for multiplet, and “br” for broad. ¹H spectra were referenced residual solvent peaks with respect to TMS (δ = 0 ppm).

Photophysical measurements. Optically dilute solutions of concentrations on the order of 10^{-5} or 10^{-6} M of the photocatalysts were prepared in spectroscopic or HPLC grade solvents for absorption and emission analysis. Absorption spectra were recorded at room temperature on a Shimadzu UV-2600 double beam spectrophotometer and a Varian Cary 50 BIO spectrophotometer with a 1 cm quartz cuvette or a Hellma ultra-micro cuvette with 3 mm optical path length. Molar absorptivity determination was verified by linear regression analysis of values obtained from five independent solutions at varying concentrations with absorbance ranging from 4.12×10^{-6} to 2.06×10^{-5} M. For emission studies, aerated solutions were bubbled by compressed air for 5 minutes and spectra were taken using the cuvette for absorption analysis. Degassed solutions were prepared via four freeze-pump-thaw cycles and spectra were taken using home-made Schlenk quartz cuvette. Steady-state emission, excitation spectra and time-resolved emission spectra were recorded at 298 K using an Edinburgh Instruments F980 or a Perkin Elmer LS55 spectrofluorometer, equipped with a Hamamatsu R928 phototube. Samples were excited at 360 nm or 420 nm for steady-state measurements and at 378 nm or 340 nm for time-resolved measurements.

The singlet-triplet splitting energy ΔE_{ST} was estimated by recording the prompt fluorescence spectra and phosphorescence emission at 77 K. An open Dewar was used for solution samples. The samples were photoexcited using the third harmonic emission (343 nm) from a femtosecond Nd:YAG laser, which originally emits at 1030 nm (Orpheus-N, model: PN13F1). Emission from the samples was focused onto a spectrograph (Chromex imaging, 250is spectrograph) and detected on a sensitive gated iCCD camera (Stanford Computer Optics, 4Picos) having subnanosecond resolution. Phosphorescence spectra were measured 1 ms after the excitation of the Nd:YAG laser with iCCD exposure time of 8.5 ms. Prompt fluorescence spectra were measured 1 ns after the excitation of the femtosecond laser with iCCD exposure time of 100 ns.

Fitting of time-resolved luminescence measurements: Time-resolved PL measurements were fitted to a sum of exponentials decay model, with chi-squared (χ^2) values between 1 and 2, using the EI FLS980 or Edinburgh FLS920 software. Each component of the decay is assigned a weight, (w_i), which is the contribution of the emission from each component to the total emission.

Emission quantum yield measurements: Emission quantum yields were measured following the method of Demas and Crosby¹¹ using $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3]^{2+}$ as the standard in air-equilibrated aqueous solution $\Phi = 0.0405$.¹²

Electrochemistry measurements. Cyclic Voltammetry (CV) analysis was performed on an Electrochemical Analyzer potentiostat model 620E from CH Instruments at a sweep rate of 100 mV/s. Differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) was conducted with an increment potential of 0.004 V and a pulse amplitude, width, and period of 50 mV, 0.05, and 0.5 s, respectively. Samples were prepared as acetonitrile (MeCN), dichloromethane (DCM), tetrahydrofuran (THF) or N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF) solutions, which were degassed by sparging with solvent-saturated argon gas for 5 minutes prior to measurements. All measurements were performed using 0.1 M solution of tetra-*n*-butylammonium hexafluorophosphate ([*n*Bu₄N]PF₆). An Ag/Ag⁺ electrode was used as the reference electrode while a glassy carbon electrode and a platinum wire were used as the working electrode and counter electrode, respectively. The redox potentials are reported relative to a saturated calomel electrode (SCE) with a ferrocenium/ferrocene (Fc/Fc⁺) redox couple as the internal standard (0.38 V vs SCE for MeCN,¹³ 0.46 V vs SCE for DCM, 0.56 V vs SCE for THF and 0.45 V vs SCE for DMF).¹⁴

Theoretical Calculations. All ground state optimizations have been carried out using Density Functional Theory (DFT) level with Gaussian 16¹⁵ using the PBE0 functional¹⁶ and the 6-31G(d,p) basis set,¹⁷ except for triplet excited state optimizations, where calculations at the same level of theory were made using unrestricted DFT. All calculations employed a polarizable continuum model (PCM) to simulate the solvent environment for each of the solvents MeCN, DMF, DCM and THF. Excited state calculations were performed using Time-Dependent DFT (TD-DFT) using the same functional and basis set as for ground state geometry optimization. Calculations were automated using an in-house designed software package, *Silico*, which uses a number of 3rd party libraries and programs, including: extraction and processing of results: cclib,¹⁸ generation of 3D images: VMD¹⁹ & Tachyon,²⁰ generation of graphs: Matplotlib,²¹ calculation of CIE colour coordinates: Colour Science,²² generation of report: Mako²³ & Weasyprint,²⁴ scientific constants: SciPy,²⁵ conversion of file formats: Pybe²⁶ & Openbabel.²⁷ Structures were visualized with *Gaussview* v5.0. *GaussSum*3.0 was used to and visualize simulated absorption spectra (full-width at half maximum set to 1000 cm⁻¹). *Chemission* v4.67 was used to model atom group contributions to the frontier molecular orbitals.

Synthesis

pDTCz-DPmS was synthesised according to a modified literature procedure in 4 steps.²⁸

Step 1: Synthesis of 9-(5-bromopyrimidin-2-yl)-3,6-di-*tert*-butyl-9H-carbazole (tCz-BrPm) was completed according to literature procedure.²⁸

Figure S1. Reaction scheme for the synthesis of tCz-BrPm.

To an oven dried flask were added 5-bromo-2-iodopyrimidine (1.57 g, 5.5 mmol, 1 equiv.), di-*tert*-butyl-9Hcarbazole (1.7 g, 6.1 mmol, 1.1 equiv.), copper powder (0.35 g, 5.5 mmol, 1 equiv.) and potassium carbonate (2.28 g, 16.5 mmol, 3 equiv.). The flask was degassed by three cycles of vacuum-nitrogen purging and 12 mL of dry chlorobenzene was injected. The mixture was stirred at 140 °C using an oil bath for 18 h under a nitrogen atmosphere. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool before being then poured into water (30 mL) and extracted with DCM (3 × 20 mL). The combined organic layers were dried over anhydrous MgSO₄, filtered and the solvent removed under reduced pressure. The crude product was purified by silica gel column chromatography. DCM:Hexane =1:3 was used as eluent to afford tCz-BrPm as a white solid. **Yield:** 1.70 g, 71%. **R_f:** 0.65 (33% DCM:Hexane). **¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃), δ (ppm):** 8.80 (s, 2H), 8.69 (d, 2H), 8.04 (dd, 2H), 7.54 (dd, 2H), 1.46 (s, 18H). The ¹H NMR spectrum is consistent with the literature.²⁸

Step 2: Synthesis of 9-(5-iodopyrimidin-2-yl)-3,6-di-*tert*-butyl-9H-carbazole (tCz-IPm)

Figure S2. Reaction scheme for the synthesis of tCz-IPm.

To an oven dried flask were added tCz-BrPm (0.67 g, 1.54 mmol, 1 equiv.), NaI (0.915 g, 6.14 mmol, 4 equiv.) and CuI (0.029 g, 0.154 mmol, 0.1 equiv.). The flask was degassed by three cycles of vacuum-nitrogen purging and 24 mL of dry DMF was injected alongside *trans*-1,2-cyclohexanediamine (0.037 mL, 0.307 mmol, 0.2 equiv.). The mixture was stirred at $145\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ using an oil bath for 17 h under a nitrogen atmosphere. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool before being poured onto H_2O (40 mL) and extracted with DCM ($3 \times 50\text{ mL}$). The combined organic layers were dried over MgSO_4 and the organic solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The crude product was purified by washing with acetone to obtain a white solid which was a mix of the tCz-IPm and tCz-BrPm. The product was used for the next step without further purification.

Step 3: synthesis of bis(2-(3,6-di-*tert*-butyl-9H-carbazol-9-yl) pyrimidin-5-yl) sulfane (tCz-PmS).

Figure S3. Reaction scheme for the synthesis of tCz-PmS.

To an oven dried flask were added tCz-IPm (1.38 g, 2.86 mmol, 1 equiv.), sodium sulfide nonahydrate (0.247 g, 1.03 mmol, 0.6 equiv.) CuI (0.033 g, 0.28 mmol, 0.1 equiv.) and K_2CO_3 (0.710 g, 5.14 mmol, 3 equiv.). The flask was degassed by three cycles of vacuum-nitrogen purging and 20 mL of dry DMF was injected. The mixture was stirred at $145\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ using an oil bath for 20 h under a nitrogen atmosphere. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool before

being poured into 75 mL of icy water and extracted with ethyl acetate (3×40 mL). The combined organic layers were dried over MgSO_4 and the organic solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The crude product was purified by silica gel column chromatography. DCM:Hexane=1:1 was used as eluent to afford tCz-PmS as a white solid. **Yield:** 746 mg, 35%. **Rf:** 0.52 (33% DCM:Hexane). **$^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3), δ (ppm):** 8.87 (s, 4H), 8.75 (dd, 4H), 8.04 (d, 4H), 7.53 (dd, 4H), 1.46 (s, 36H). The $^1\text{H NMR}$ spectrum is consistent with the literature.²⁸

Step 4: synthesis of 9,9'-(sulfonylbis(pyrimidine-5,2-diyl))bis(3,6-di-*tert*-butyl-9H-carbazole) (**pDTCz-DPmS**) was completed according to literature procedure.²⁸

Figure S4. Reaction scheme for the synthesis of **pDTCz-DPmS**.

To a flask were added tCz-PmS (0.302 g, 0.41 mmol, 1 equiv.) and acetic acid (8 mL). To this suspension was added H_2O_2 (30 wt%, 12 mL, 1 equiv.) and mixture was heated to 85 °C using an oil bath for 18 h. The mixture was then poured into 40 mL of icy water and extracted with DCM (3×25 mL). The combined organic layers were dried over MgSO_4 , filtered and the organic solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The crude product was purified by silica gel column chromatography. DCM:Hexanes = 4:1 was used as the eluent to afford **pDTCz-DPmS** as a white solid. The product was further purified by recrystallization in DCM:Hexanes. **Yield:** 124 mg, 39%. **Rf:** 0.68 (75% DCM:Hexane). **Mp:** 292-294 °C. **Lit.:** 292-294 °C.²⁸ **$^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm):** 9.31 (s, 4H), 8.84 (d, $J = 8.9$ Hz, 4H), 8.04 (d, $J = 2.0$ Hz, 4H), 7.57 (dd, $J = 8.9, 2.0$ Hz, 4H), 1.48 (s, 36H). The $^1\text{H NMR}$ spectrum is consistent with that in the literature.²⁸

Electrochemistry

Figure S5. CVs and DPVs of a) 4CzIPN and b) pDTCz-DPmS in a range of solvents, reported vs SCE at scan rate of 0.1 V s^{-1} .

Table S1. Redox potentials and optical gaps for **4CzIPN** and **pDTCz-DPmS**.^a

PC		THF	DCM	DMF	MeCN
4CzIPN	E_{ox} / V		1.51		1.50
	$E_{\text{red}} / \text{V}$	-1.20	-1.21	-1.24	-1.24
	$E^*_{\text{ox}} / \text{V}$		-1.09		-1.15
	$E^*_{\text{red}} / \text{V}$	1.46	1.39	1.40	1.41
	$E_{0,0} / \text{eV}$	2.66	2.60	2.64	2.65
pDTCz-DPmS	E_{ox} / V		1.57		
	$E_{\text{red}} / \text{V}$	-1.77	-1.67	-1.62	
	$E^*_{\text{ox}} / \text{V}$		-1.44		
	$E^*_{\text{red}} / \text{V}$	1.32	1.34	1.48	
	$E_{0,0} / \text{eV}$	3.09	3.01	3.10	

^aAll redox potentials are reported vs SCE. E_{ox} and E_{red} values obtained from DPV max and $E^*_{\text{ox}} = E_{\text{ox}} - E_{0,0}$ and $E^*_{\text{red}} = E_{\text{red}} + E_{0,0}$. $E_{0,0}$ obtained from the intersection point between the normalized absorption and emission spectra.

Photophysical measurements

Figure S6. Solvatochromic absorption study for a) 4CzIPN and b) pDTCz-DPmS and solvatochromic PL study of c) 4CzIPN and d) pDTCz-DPmS. $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 420 \text{ nm}$ for 4CzIPN and 360 nm for pDTCz-DPmS. Measurements performed at room temperature under air.

Table S2. Absorption and emission maxima of **4CzIPN** and **pDTCz-DPmS** in different solvents.

Solvent	$\lambda_{\text{abs}} / \text{nm}$ ($\epsilon / 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)		$\lambda_{\text{PL}} / \text{nm}$		$E_{0,0} / \text{eV}$	
	4CzIPN	pDTCz-DPmS	4CzIPN	pDTCz-DPmS	4CzIPN	pDTCz-DPmS
Toluene	441 (6)	365 (59)	507	480	2.59	3.12
THF	438 (8)	357 (58)	525	505	2.66	3.09
DCM	448 (7)	363 (64)	544	524	2.60	3.01
DMF	428 (6)	355 (57)	554	535	2.64	3.10
MeCN	432 (6)		560	546	2.65	

Figure S7. Time resolved PL decay of **pDTCz-DPmS** recorded in a) THF, b) DCM and c) DMF under vacuum in 10^{-5} M solutions with $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 378$ nm.

Figure S8. Prompt fluorescence and phosphorescence spectra of **pDTCz-DPmS** in a) THF, b) DCM, c) DMF, d) toluene and e) BuCN measured in 10^{-5} M solutions at 77 K. In all cases, $\lambda_{exc} = 343$ nm, and prompt and delayed fluorescence spectra were obtained in the 1–100 ns and 1–8.5 ms time range, respectively

Mechanistic studies of the decarboxylative addition reaction of *N*-Cbz-Pro to diethyl maleate

Figure S9. Absorption spectra of **pDTCz-DPmS** (black line, 4×10^{-5} M), diethylmaleate (red line, 5×10^{-4} M) and *N*-Cbz-Pro (green line, 5×10^{-4} M) in DMF.

Figure S9 demonstrates that the photocatalyst **pDTCz-DPmS** is the only species absorbing the 390 nm LED light in the decarboxylative addition of *N*-Cbz-Pro to diethyl maleate.

Figure S10. Stern-Volmer plot of the quenching of the TADF emission of **pDTCz-DPmS** in DMF by sequential addition of diethylmaleate.

Figure S11. Time resolved PL decay of a deaerated solution of **pDTCz-DPmS** (4.27×10^{-5} M, black line) in DMF and after addition of: a) *N*-Cbz-Pro (0.05 M) and K_2HPO_4 (saturated solution) and b) diethyl maleate (0.055 M) with $\lambda_{exc} = 340$ nm.

The quenching process is studied following the changes in the lifetime of the delayed emission of the photocatalyst by addition of increasing amounts of diethylmaleate or *N*-Cbz-Pro. The photocatalyst is not quenched by the protonated form of *N*-Cbz-Pro; deprotonation of the carboxylic acid is required. The quenching of the deprotonated form of *N*-Cbz-Pro is evaluated after the addition of *N*-Cbz-Pro and K_2HPO_4 and 12 hours of stirring under inert atmosphere.

To evaluate the quenching of **pDTCz-DPmS** under the reaction conditions, we evaluated the quenching efficiency of species *i* according to the following formula:

$$\eta^i = \frac{k_q^i \cdot [Q]^i}{k_{nr} + k_r + \sum_0^n k_q^i \cdot [Q]^i} \cdot 100$$

where $k_{nr} + k_r = \frac{1}{\tau_0}$ are the intramolecular deactivation pathways and k_q^i is the quenching constant of the quencher species *i*.

Figure S12. Time resolved PL decay of a deaerated solution of **4CzIPN** (5.6×10^{-5} M, black line) in DMF and after addition of *N*-Cbz-Pro (0.05 M, red line) and K_2HPO_4 (saturated solution) with $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 340$ nm.

Figure S13. UV-Vis absorption spectra of **4CzIPN**, N-Cbz-Pro and Cs₂CO₃ (1:4:4 equiv.) in DMF before and after 30 minutes of irradiation under N₂ with 390 nm Kessil lamp.

Figure S14. UV-Vis absorption spectra of **pDTCz-DPmS**, N-Cbz-Pro and Cs₂CO₃ (1:4:4 equiv.) in DMF before and after 30 minutes of irradiation under N₂ with 390 nm Kessil lamp.

Figure S15. UV-Vis absorption spectra of **4CzIPN**, N-Cbz-Pro, K_2HPO_4 and diethyl maleate (0.02 : 1 : 1.1 : 1.1 ratio as in the reaction) in DMF before and after 24 minutes of irradiation under N_2 with 390 nm Kessil lamp.

Figure S16. UV-Vis absorption spectra of **pDTCz-DPmS**, N-Cbz-Pro, K_2HPO_4 and diethyl maleate (0.02 : 1 : 1.1 : 1.1 ratio as in the reaction) in DMF before and after 24 minutes of irradiation under N_2 with 390 nm Kessil lamp.

Figure S17. CV and DPV of diethyl maleate (black), *N*-Cbz-Pro (red) and *tert*-butylammonium *N*-Cbz-Pro salt (green) all in DMF, reported vs SCE at scan rate of 0.1 V s^{-1} . Due to the absence of electrochemical activity in the window scanned, only the CV was obtained for *N*-Cbz-Pro. CV and DPV of [TBA][*N*-Cbz-Pro] was obtained according to the procedure outlined in reference ²⁹.

Figure S18. ¹H NMR of diethyl maleate reagent with integration of the relevant peaks corresponding to the *Z* maleate isomer (6.23 ppm) and the *E* fumarate isomer (6.85 ppm) in CDCl₃.

Figure S19. ^1H NMR obtained in CDCl_3 after irradiation of diethyl maleate in the presence of **pDTCz-DPmS**, according to the reaction conditions and concentrations outlined for the decarboxylative addition of *N*-Cbz-Pro to diethyl maleate, but in the absence of *N*-Cbz-Pro and K_2HPO_4 . The integrated peaks shown correspond to the *Z* maleate isomer (6.23 ppm) and the *E* fumarate isomer (6.85 ppm).

From the ^1H NMR data shown in Figures S18 and S19, we can conclude that no $Z \rightarrow E$ isomerisation of diethyl maleate is taking place upon irradiation with **pDTCz-DPmS**.

Photocatalysis

Photocatalysis experiments were conducted using a custom-built photoreactor, as shown in Figure S20, allowing for up to 8 parallel photochemical reactions (7 mL) at a time. The photochemistry reaction chamber is filled with mirrors to evenly distribute light. The reactor is placed upon a magnetic stirrer plate allowing for reactions to be completed with stirring. Reactions are irradiated using Kessil PR160 LED sources. For Kessil PR160-390 nm, the chosen LED source for photocatalysis reactions completed in this study, the power consumption maximum is 52 W, with the average intensity measured from 1 cm distance being 352 mW cm^{-2} . The intensity on each lamp is tuneable, with the maximum intensity selected for all photocatalytic reactions. A cooling fan is directed at the photoreactor to ensure the reaction mixture maintains at room temperature, which is further guaranteed by the presence of two fans on the photoreactor itself.

After the photoreactions were completed, the products were analysed by ^1H NMR spectroscopy with an internal standard, either 1,3,5-trimethoxybenzene or 1,4-(bis(trimethylsilyl)benzene). All yields shown represent the mean yield from at least two reactions with the associated standard deviation.

Figure S20. Experimental setup for photocatalysis reactions.

Procedure for oxidative quenching reaction:

Figure S21. Reaction scheme for the oxidative quenching reaction.

To an oven-dried vial was added *p*-toluenesulfonyl chloride (48 mg, 0.25 mmol, 1 equiv.) styrene (0.017 mL, 0.25 mmol, 1 equiv.) and photocatalyst (1 mol%, 0.0025 mmol). The vial was purged with N₂ for 5 min and dry DCM (1.0 mL) was added before further N₂ purging for 10 min. The solution was stirred at room temperature while being irradiated by Kessil lamp ($\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 390 \text{ nm}$) for 24 hours. After removal of solvent, the crude product was purified by flash column chromatography (5:1 hexane:EtOAc) to afford the final product as a white solid. **R_f**: 0.30 (5:1 hexane:EtOAc). **¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃), δ (ppm):** 7.63 (d, 2H), 7.29 – 7.22 (m, 7H), 5.33 (t, 1H), 3.94 (dd, 1H), 3.85 (dd, 1H), 2.41 (s, 3H). The ¹H NMR spectrum is consistent with that in the literature.³⁰

Table S3. ¹H NMR yields obtained from the oxidative quench reaction.^a

Photocatalyst	$\lambda_{\text{exc}} / \text{nm}$	Solvent	¹ H NMR yield / %
None	390	MeCN	0
[Ru(bpy) ₃](PF ₆) ₂	456	MeCN	81 ± 1
[Ru(bpy) ₃](PF ₆) ₂	390	MeCN	42 ± 1
[Ru(bpy) ₃](PF ₆) ₂	390	DCM	64 ± 3
4CzIPN	390	DCM	10 ± 1
pDTCz-DPmS	390	DCM	16 ± 2

^a Reaction conditions as stated in the procedure above unless otherwise noted.

Procedure for reductive quenching reaction:

1) Pinacol coupling

Figure S22. Reaction scheme for the pinacol coupling.

To an oven-dried vial was added benzaldehyde (0.020 mL, 0.2 mmol, 1 equiv.), DIPEA (0.174 mL, 1 mmol, 5 equiv.) and photocatalyst (1 mol%, 0.002 mmol). The vial was purged with N₂ for 5 min and dry DMF (2.0 mL) was added before further N₂ purging for 10 min. The solution

was stirred at room temperature while being irradiated by Kessil lamp ($\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 390 \text{ nm}$) for 2 or 24 hours. After removal of solvent, the crude product was purified by flash column chromatography (1:5 EtOAc:Hexane \rightarrow 100% EtOAc) to afford the product as a white solid. **R_f**: 0.83 (100% EtOAc). **¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) of meso and dl, δ (ppm):** 7.33 – 7.27 (m, 6H), 7.26 – 7.21 (m, 10H), 7.12 (dd, $J = 6.5, 2.9 \text{ Hz}$, 4H, dl), 4.81 (s, 2H, meso), 4.66 (s, 2H, dl), 3.17 (br s, 2H, dl), 2.50 (br s, 2H, meso). The ¹H NMR spectrum is consistent with that in the literature.³¹

Table S4. ¹H NMR yields obtained from the pinacol reaction.^a

Photocatalyst	Time / h	¹ H NMR yield / %
None	2	18 \pm 2
None	24	50 \pm 2
[Ir(ppy) ₂ (dtbbpy)]PF ₆	2	43 \pm 3
[Ir(ppy) ₂ (dtbbpy)]PF ₆	24	74 \pm 3
4CzIPN	2	68 \pm 0
4CzIPN	24	76 \pm 3
pDTCz-DPmS	2	32 \pm 1
pDTCz-DPmS	24	80 \pm 3

^a Reaction conditions as stated in the procedure above unless otherwise noted.

2) Decarboxylative addition of *N*-Cbz-Pro to diethyl maleate

Figure S23. Reaction scheme for the decarboxylative addition of *N*-Cbz-Pro to diethyl maleate.

To an oven-dried vial was added *N*-Cbz-Pro (50 mg, 0.2 mmol, 1 equiv.), K₂HPO₄ (38 mg, 0.22 mmol, 1.1 equiv.), diethyl maleate (0.036 mL, 0.22 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and photocatalyst (2 mol%, 0.004 mmol). The vial was purged with N₂ for 5 min and dry DMF (4.0 mL) was added before further N₂ purging for 10 min. The solution was stirred at room temperature while being irradiated by Kessil lamp ($\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 390 \text{ nm}$) for 24 hours. After irradiation, the mixture was poured into water and extracted with DCM (3 \times 15 mL). The combined organic phases were dried over Na₂SO₄ and filtered. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the residue was purified by flash chromatography on silica gel (3-20% EtOAc:Hexane) to afford the product as a colourless solid. **R_f**: 0.19 (1:4 EtOAc:Hexane). **¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃), δ (ppm):** 7.49

– 7.31 (m, 5H), 5.30 – 5.03 (m, 2H), 4.38 – 4.28 (m, 1H), 4.24 – 4.02 (m, 4H), 3.77 – 3.46 (m, 2H), 3.44 – 3.20 (m, 1H), 2.88 – 2.66 (m, 1H), 2.57 – 2.24 (m, 1H), 2.01 – 1.72 (m, 4H), 1.32 – 1.16 (m, 6H). The ^1H NMR spectrum is consistent with that in the literature.³²

Table S5. ^1H NMR yields obtained from the decarboxylative addition of *N*-Cbz-Pro to diethyl maleate.^a

Photocatalyst	^1H NMR yield / %
None	0
$[\text{Ir}(\text{dF}(\text{CF}_3)\text{ppy})_2(\text{dtbbpy})]\text{PF}_6$	99 ± 0
4CzIPN	99 ± 0
pDTCz-DPmS	64 ± 3

^a Reaction conditions as stated in the procedure above.

Procedure for *E/Z* isomerisation reaction:

Figure S24. Reaction scheme for the *E/Z* isomerisation of a) *E*-stilbene and b) diisopropyl fumarate.

To an oven-dried vial was added *E*-stilbene (36 mg, 0.2 mmol, 1 equiv.) or diisopropyl fumarate (0.039 mL, 0.2 mmol, 1 equiv.) and photocatalyst (0.7 mol%, 0.0014 mmol). The vial was purged with N_2 for 5 min and dry DMF (1.0 mL) was added before further N_2 purging for 10 min. The solution was stirred at room temperature while being irradiated by Kessil lamp ($\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 390 \text{ nm}$) for 18 or 24 hours (for *E*-stilbene and diisopropyl fumarate, respectively). After removal of solvent, the crude product was purified by flash column chromatography.

Z-stilbene: white solid. **R_f**: 0.27 (*n*-pentane). **^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3)**, δ (ppm): 7.29-7.16 (m, 10H), 6.61 (s, 2H). The ^1H NMR spectrum is consistent with that in the literature.³³

Diisopropyl maleate: colourless oil. **R_f**: 0.20 (1:20 EtOAc:Petroleum ether). **^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3)**, δ (ppm): 6.18 (s, 2 H), 5.11 (sept, 2H), 1.29 (d, 12 H). The ^1H NMR spectrum is consistent with that in the literature.³⁴

Table S6. ¹H NMR yields obtained for the E/Z isomerisation of alkenes.^a

Photocatalyst	Substrate	¹ H NMR yield / %
None	<i>E</i> -Stilbene	5 ± 0
None	diisopropyl fumarate	Trace
[Ru(bpy) ₃](PF ₆) ₂	<i>E</i> -Stilbene	81 ± 1
[Ir(dF(CF ₃)ppy) ₂ (dtbbpy)]PF ₆	diisopropyl fumarate	58 ± 1
4CzIPN	<i>E</i> -Stilbene	87 ± 1
4CzIPN	diisopropyl fumarate	6 ± 1
pDTCz-DPmS	<i>E</i> -Stilbene	63 ± 4
pDTCz-DPmS	diisopropyl fumarate	81 ± 2

^a Reaction conditions as stated in the procedure above unless otherwise noted.

Procedure for dual Ni(II) cross-coupling reaction:

Figure S25. Reaction scheme for the dual Ni(II) cross-coupling reaction.

To an oven-dried vial was added *p*-bromobenzonitrile (36 mg, 0.2 mmol, 1 equiv.), *N*-Cbz-proline (74 mg, 0.3 mmol, 1.5 equiv.), NiCl₂.DME (4.4 mg, 20 μmol, 10 mol%), 2,2'-bipyridine (4.7 mg, 30 μmol, 15 mol%), Cs₂CO₃ (98 mg, 0.3 mmol, 1.5 equiv.) and photocatalyst (2.5 mol%, 0.005 mmol). The vial was purged with N₂ for 5 mins before the additions of dry DMF (5.0 mL) and a further 10 min of N₂ purging. The reaction mixture and stirred and irradiated with a Kessil lamp (λ_{exc} = 390 nm) for 24 hours. Upon completion, the mixture was added to H₂O (10 mL) and extracted with EtOAc (3 x 15 mL). The combined organic layers were dried over MgSO₄, filtered and the solvent removed *in vacuo*. The crude product was purified by flash column chromatography (15:85 EtOAc:Hexane) to afford the product as a foam. **R_f**: 0.14 (15:85 EtOAc:Hexane). **¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃)**, δ (ppm): 7.57 (dd, 2H), 7.37 – 7.17 (m, 6H), 6.89 (d, 1H), 5.16 – 4.99 (m, 2H), 4.94 – 4.87 (m, 1H), 3.72 – 3.64 (m, 2H), 2.43 – 2.31 (m, 1H), 1.94 – 1.78 (m, 3H). ¹H The ¹H NMR spectrum is consistent with that in the literature.³⁵

Table S7. ¹H NMR yields for the dual Ni(II) cross-coupling reaction.^a

Photocatalyst	¹ H NMR yield / %
None	24 ± 0
4CzIPN	99 ± 1
pDTCz-DPmS	72 ± 4

^a Reaction conditions as stated in the procedure above.

NMR

2204141412-2-33-mab30.10.fid
MAB-IV43-130422 product after acetone wash || 1H Observe

Figure S26. ¹H NMR spectrum of 9-(5-bromopyrimidin-2-yl)-3,6-di-*tert*-butyl-9H-carbazole (tCz-BrPm) in CDCl₃ at 400 MHz.

2204191506-0-18-mab30.10.fid
MAB-IV47-180422 solid after acetone wash || 1H Observe

Figure S27. ¹H NMR spectrum of the mixture of 9-(5-bromopyrimidin-2-yl)-3,6-di-*tert*-butyl-9H-carbazole (tCz-BrPm) and 9-(5-iodopyrimidin-2-yl)-3,6-di-*tert*-butyl-9H-carbazole (tCz-IPm) in CDCl₃ at 400 MHz.

2204261144-2-16-mab30.10.fid
MAB-IV49 F6 solid || 1H Observe

Figure S28. ¹H NMR spectrum of bis(2-(3,6-di-*tert*-butyl-9H-carbazol-9-yl)pyrimidin-5-yl)sulfane (tCz-PmS) in CDCl₃ at 400 MHz.

Figure S29. ^1H NMR spectrum of 9,9'-(sulfonylbis(pyrimidine-5,2-diyl))bis(3,6-di-*tert*-butyl-9H-carbazole) (**pDTCz-DPmS**) in CDCl_3 at 400 MHz.

2202031554-2-54-fdm3.10.fid
FM-II-3700 Fractions 7-11 || 1H Observe

Figure S30. ^1H NMR spectrum of 1-((2-chloro-2-phenylethyl)sulfonyl)-4-methylbenzene in CDCl_3 at 400 MHz.

2112131444-3-7-mab30.10.fid
mab-IV33-91221 F23-24 || 1H Observe

Figure S31. ^1H NMR spectrum of 1,2-diphenylethane-1,2-diol in CDCl_3 at 400 MHz.

2112141540-3-32-mab30.10.fid
MAV-IV29-11221 F28-33 dried || 1H Observe

Figure S32. ^1H NMR spectrum of diethyl 2-(1-((benzyloxy)carbonyl)pyrrolidine-2-yl)succinate in CDCl_3 at 400 MHz.

11132020-4-ezc-mab30-R.10.fid
1H Observe
MAB-II44-101120 F32-39

Figure S33. ^1H NMR spectrum of *Z*-stilbene in CDCl_3 at 400 MHz.

04092021-13-ezc-mab30-M.10.fid
1H Observe
MAB-II123-70421 Z-isomer maleate

Figure S34. ^1H NMR spectrum of diisopropyl maleate in CDCl_3 at 400 MHz.

Figure S35. ¹H NMR spectrum of benzyl 2-(4-cyanophenyl)pyrrolidine-1-carboxylate in CDCl₃ at 400 MHz.

DFT calculations

Table S8. Selected data from DFT calculations for **pDTCz-DPmS**.

Selected data from DFT calculations:	MeCN	DCM	THF	DMF
HOMO / eV	-6.08	-6.06	-6.05	-6.08
LUMO / eV	-1.90	-1.89	-1.89	-1.90
$\Delta E_{\text{HOMO-LUMO}}$ / eV	4.18	4.17	4.16	4.18
Ground state dipole moment magnitude / D	5.91	5.75	5.72	5.91
S_1 / eV	3.47	3.47	3.47	3.47
T_1 / eV	2.98	2.97	2.97	2.98
ΔE_{ST} / eV	0.49	0.50	0.50	0.49
Dipole moment in the T_1 state / D	16.32	19.56	15.22	16.32
Predicted Phosphorescence at RT / eV	2.71	2.51	2.75	2.71
Imaginary frequencies	0	0	0	0

Figure S36. (a) Orbital contributions calculated from DFT results in each of the solvents modelled (MeCN, DCM, THF and DMF) for **pDTCz-DPmS** and (b) the simulated UV-Vis absorption spectra of **pDTCz-DPmS** from DFT calculations in MeCN, DCM, THF and DMF compared with the experimental data obtained in THF. Simulated spectra were generated with a full-width at half maximum set to 1000 cm^{-1} .

Figure S37. Energy level diagram for **pDTCz-DPmS** in the different solvents.

Cartesian coordinates of pDTCz-DPmS in THF

Element	X Coord	Y Coord	Z Coord
S	0.0000010	0.0001030	4.2336010
O	0.0224710	1.2772260	4.9491880
N	2.9794050	-1.2251740	1.8642430
N	3.0945490	1.1577870	1.9890660
N	4.5966140	-0.0428330	0.6951070
C	1.9299920	-1.2094640	2.6676050
H	1.4976600	-2.1699460	2.9399890
C	1.3996950	-0.0192120	3.1629480
C	2.0437800	1.1588680	2.7911890
H	1.7026630	2.1209580	3.1666050
C	3.5177370	-0.0364830	1.5442090
C	5.3004380	1.1003120	0.2334440
C	5.1304740	2.4580900	0.4846200
H	4.3482150	2.8115870	1.1385480
C	6.0022940	3.3542480	-0.1322570
H	5.8574160	4.4086890	0.0735550
C	7.0364680	2.9518880	-0.9887250
C	7.1874670	1.5832300	-1.2251510
H	7.9740860	1.2195440	-1.8802780
C	6.3318380	0.6691510	-0.6232720
C	6.2667690	-0.7731640	-0.6937490
C	7.0452660	-1.6956950	-1.3898430
H	7.8599410	-1.3353480	-2.0081800
C	6.7736510	-3.0575220	-1.2862010
C	5.7009790	-3.4491930	-0.4650270
H	5.4679430	-4.5053920	-0.3655030
C	4.9089620	-2.5500970	0.2388170
H	4.0952450	-2.8945730	0.8583750
C	5.1999430	-1.1913570	0.1192840
C	7.9868130	3.9438980	-1.6595460
C	7.6720690	5.3933190	-1.2855900
H	6.6624380	5.6825210	-1.5950610

H	7.7652730	5.5640990	-0.2081590
H	8.3775210	6.0611990	-1.7896230
C	7.8716410	3.8030160	-3.1849140
H	6.8524330	4.0205590	-3.5200260
H	8.5522370	4.5030050	-3.6817580
H	8.1277370	2.7931910	-3.5189090

Cartesian coordinates of **pDTCz-DPmS** in DCM

Element	X Coord	Y Coord	Z Coord
S	0.0000000	0.0000330	4.2290140
O	0.0225340	1.2768860	4.9453340
N	2.9808350	-1.2254980	1.8618250
N	3.0950860	1.1575310	1.9854290
N	4.5986710	-0.0432820	0.6934380
C	1.9308280	-1.2098190	2.6644720
H	1.4985250	-2.1703200	2.9367240
C	1.4000430	-0.0194130	3.1589590
C	2.0437580	1.1587700	2.7868670
H	1.7019140	2.1210260	3.1611260
C	3.5189590	-0.0368240	1.5416640
C	5.3036860	1.0997030	0.2332940
C	5.1340050	2.4575110	0.4847430
H	4.3508060	2.8112280	1.1374430
C	6.0072920	3.3535130	-0.1303600
H	5.8625420	4.4079340	0.0756490
C	7.0426720	2.9509920	-0.9853590
C	7.1933570	1.5823310	-1.2221870
H	7.9807910	1.2185000	-1.8762510
C	6.3362610	0.6684300	-0.6220230
C	6.2705070	-0.7738280	-0.6933290
C	7.0494730	-1.6964130	-1.3889180
H	7.8653030	-1.3361780	-2.0057990
C	6.7766970	-3.0581450	-1.2866710
C	5.7023930	-3.4496520	-0.4674780

H	5.4682870	-4.5057320	-0.3692000
C	4.9099670	-2.5504780	0.2358690
H	4.0950310	-2.8949160	0.8538650
C	5.2021750	-1.1918180	0.1179000
C	7.9945760	3.9428450	-1.6542180
C	7.6800740	5.3922320	-1.2799260
H	6.6710900	5.6822040	-1.5907900
H	7.7716830	5.5623670	-0.2022530
H	8.3867340	6.0599190	-1.7825150
C	7.8816250	3.8028160	-3.1798380
H	6.8630910	4.0213600	-3.5163950
H	8.5634730	4.5026250	-3.6751990
H	8.1375750	2.7929940	-3.5139600

C	9.4351790	3.6336900	-1.2194350
H	10.1318830	4.3324890	-1.6951740
H	9.5430280	3.7284950	-0.1341840
H	9.7343250	2.6196070	-1.5005960
C	7.5933190	-4.1204170	-2.0211310
C	8.2257670	-5.0729360	-0.9952130
H	8.8109830	-5.8447700	-1.5069070
H	8.8935100	-4.5288940	-0.3195460
H	7.4675030	-5.5755180	-0.3876790
C	6.6690830	-4.9162550	-2.9550650
H	7.2404170	-5.6855270	-3.4859150
H	5.8676300	-5.4161270	-2.4032420
H	6.2077280	-4.2585620	-3.6987130
C	8.7135600	-3.5059310	-2.8619480
H	9.2691230	-4.3015230	-3.3678930
H	8.3206690	-2.8338250	-3.6319170
H	9.4236030	-2.9461390	-2.2443980
O	-0.0225340	-1.2768040	4.9453620
N	-2.9808360	1.2255120	1.8618010
N	-3.0950860	-1.1575140	1.9854550
N	-4.5986710	0.0432760	0.6934380
C	-1.9308290	1.2098500	2.6644470
H	-1.4985260	2.1703570	2.9366790
C	-1.4000430	0.0194550	3.1589590
C	-2.0437570	-1.1587360	2.7868920
H	-1.7019120	-2.1209840	3.1611700
C	-3.5189600	0.0368310	1.5416650
C	-5.3036890	-1.0997120	0.2333020
C	-5.1340100	-2.4575190	0.4847580
H	-4.3508130	-2.8112350	1.1374600
C	-6.0072980	-3.3535230	-0.1303400
H	-5.8625500	-4.4079440	0.0756740
C	-7.0426780	-2.9510050	-0.9853420
C	-7.1933590	-1.5823450	-1.2221780
H	-7.9807930	-1.2185160	-1.8762440
C	-6.3362620	-0.6684430	-0.6220180
C	-6.2705060	0.7738140	-0.6933340
C	-7.0494700	1.6963980	-1.3889280
H	-7.8653010	1.3361600	-2.0058080
C	-6.7766910	3.0581300	-1.2866900

C	-5.7023870	3.4496390	-0.4674990
H	-5.4682790	4.5057190	-0.3692270
C	-4.9099620	2.5504680	0.2358540
H	-4.0950250	2.8949070	0.8538480
C	-5.2021740	1.1918080	0.1178920
C	-7.9945840	-3.9428600	-1.6541960
C	-7.6800830	-5.3922460	-1.2798970
H	-6.6711000	-5.6822200	-1.5907610
H	-7.7716910	-5.5623760	-0.2022230
H	-8.3867440	-6.0599340	-1.7824820
C	-7.8816340	-3.8028390	-3.1798160
H	-6.8631010	-4.0213850	-3.5163730
H	-8.5634840	-4.5026500	-3.6751730
H	-8.1375840	-2.7930180	-3.5139430
C	-9.4351850	-3.6337010	-1.2194130
H	-10.1318910	-4.3325010	-1.6951480
H	-9.5430340	-3.7285010	-0.1341600
H	-9.7343300	-2.6196190	-1.5005780
C	-7.5933110	4.1203990	-2.0211550
C	-8.2257390	5.0729370	-0.9952430
H	-8.8109530	5.8447700	-1.5069410
H	-8.8934810	4.5289100	-0.3195620
H	-7.4674640	5.5755190	-0.3877230
C	-6.6690790	4.9162160	-2.9551110
H	-7.2404130	5.6854840	-3.4859670
H	-5.8676170	5.4160920	-2.4033030
H	-6.2077360	4.2585080	-3.6987530
C	-8.7135670	3.5059100	-2.8619510
H	-9.2691200	4.3015000	-3.3679120
H	-8.3206910	2.8337800	-3.6319070

Cartesian coordinates of **pDTCz-DPmS** in DMF

Element	X Coord	Y Coord	Z Coord
S	0.0000020	0.0001400	4.2037210
O	0.0218390	1.2759860	4.9229360
N	2.9932990	-1.2270170	1.8545920
N	3.0958230	1.1571840	1.9614040

N	4.6111740	-0.0460740	0.6853550
C	1.9395690	-1.2109450	2.6526170
H	1.5105180	-2.1715200	2.9289910
C	1.4021410	-0.0193290	3.1368670
C	2.0412550	1.1595590	2.7587750
H	1.6930690	2.1231590	3.1233690
C	3.5268470	-0.0383140	1.5285150
C	5.3236900	1.0953980	0.2336390
C	5.1578930	2.4532650	0.4883580
H	4.3702800	2.8085860	1.1349520
C	6.0403480	3.3476080	-0.1162960
H	5.8982270	4.4019280	0.0920970
C	7.0811900	2.9434420	-0.9641750
C	7.2278070	1.5748550	-1.2048300
H	8.0189260	1.2096960	-1.8536860
C	6.3616050	0.6626690	-0.6147620
C	6.2902430	-0.7791080	-0.6915490
C	7.0697240	-1.7025460	-1.3858400
H	7.8917370	-1.3436290	-1.9952560
C	6.7887310	-3.0633770	-1.2922540
C	5.7057770	-3.4530250	-0.4833010
H	5.4644520	-4.5081430	-0.3925770
C	4.9131570	-2.5529180	0.2188930
H	4.0918370	-2.8963820	0.8290200
C	5.2139250	-1.1951340	0.1103940
C	8.0430220	3.9334920	-1.6214550
C	7.7326170	5.3827900	-1.2433950
H	6.7276010	5.6791650	-1.5610040
H	7.8163090	5.5479050	-0.1642850
H	8.4467390	6.0488130	-1.7375360
C	7.9412750	3.8001830	-3.1484970
H	6.9266530	4.0261340	-3.4921060
H	8.6307910	4.4984000	-3.6353410
H	8.1945690	2.7903710	-3.4846800

C	9.4787520	3.6153600	-1.1770070
H	10.1820630	4.3130010	-1.6445640
H	9.5788610	3.7055640	-0.0905490
H	9.7752500	2.6011230	-1.4604460
C	7.6044820	-4.1264760	-2.0265420
C	8.2207260	-5.0908260	-1.0017500
H	8.8050840	-5.8628130	-1.5141100
H	8.8865870	-4.5564720	-0.3164430
H	7.4535600	-5.5928040	-0.4049320
C	6.6827100	-4.9092550	-2.9739430
H	7.2532450	-5.6794680	-3.5042260
H	5.8725070	-5.4063910	-2.4324820
H	6.2336830	-4.2433770	-3.7179410
C	8.7366340	-3.5143230	-2.8529690
H	9.2912440	-4.3107310	-3.3586450
H	8.3556910	-2.8345990	-3.6222350
H	9.4446360	-2.9631690	-2.2253810
O	-0.0218360	-1.2756640	4.9230110
N	-2.9933100	1.2271550	1.8545360
N	-3.0958070	-1.1570420	1.9614590
N	-4.6111720	0.0461350	0.6853550
C	-1.9395790	1.2111320	2.6525620
H	-1.5105380	2.1717240	2.9288900
C	-1.4021380	0.0195440	3.1368670
C	-2.0412400	-1.1593670	2.7588300
H	-1.6930430	-2.1229470	3.1234690
C	-3.5268440	0.0384320	1.5285140
C	-5.3236530	-1.0953750	0.2336800
C	-5.1578110	-2.4532270	0.4884470
H	-4.3701860	-2.8084990	1.1350540
C	-6.0402360	-3.3476210	-0.1161750
H	-5.8980790	-4.4019290	0.0922540
C	-7.0810920	-2.9435190	-0.9640680
C	-7.2277540	-1.5749450	-1.2047710
H	-8.0188860	-1.2098340	-1.8536390
C	-6.3615820	-0.6627090	-0.6147350
C	-6.2902660	0.7790670	-0.6915730
C	-7.0697780	1.7024550	-1.3858960
H	-7.8917790	1.3434890	-1.9952990
C	-6.7888300	3.0632980	-1.2923590

C	-5.7058890	3.4530100	-0.4834190
H	-5.4645990	4.5081400	-0.3927310
C	-4.9132380	2.5529540	0.2188050
H	-4.0919290	2.8964680	0.8289190
C	-5.2139600	1.1951560	0.1103530
C	-8.0428920	-3.9336230	-1.6213120
C	-7.7324390	-5.3828980	-1.2432010
H	-6.7274130	-5.6792510	-1.5608000
H	-7.8161240	-5.5479780	-0.1640850
H	-8.4465380	-6.0489620	-1.7373180
C	-7.9411510	-3.8003650	-3.1483590
H	-6.9265220	-4.0262940	-3.4919610
H	-8.6306440	-4.4986230	-3.6351780
H	-8.1944800	-2.7905740	-3.4845770
C	-9.4786310	-3.6155240	-1.1768740
H	-10.1819200	-4.3132040	-1.6444050
H	-9.5787360	-3.7056930	-0.0904130
H	-9.7751640	-2.6013070	-1.4603480
C	-7.6046170	4.1263440	-2.0266840
C	-8.2208840	5.0907150	-1.0019270
H	-8.8052680	5.8626640	-1.5143140
H	-8.8867270	4.5563690	-0.3165970
H	-7.4537310	5.5927400	-0.4051320
C	-6.6828720	4.9091130	-2.9741200
H	-7.2534330	5.6792870	-3.5044310
H	-5.8726830	5.4062970	-2.4326830
H	-6.2338280	4.2432200	-3.7180930
C	-8.7367540	3.5141240	-2.8530820
H	-9.2913870	4.3104960	-3.3587910
H	-8.3557940	2.8343780	-3.6223200
H	-9.4447380	2.9629770	-2.2254690

Cartesian coordinates of **pDTCz-DPmS** in MeCN

Element	X Coord	Y Coord	Z Coord
S	0.0000020	0.0001410	4.2040940
O	0.0218770	1.2760010	4.9232680
N	2.9930120	-1.2269980	1.8545560

N	3.0958960	1.1571670	1.9618780
N	4.6109840	-0.0460300	0.6854660
C	1.9393410	-1.2109370	2.6526560
H	1.5101630	-2.1715100	2.9288540
C	1.4021060	-0.0193470	3.1371880
C	2.0413760	1.1595200	2.7593070
H	1.6933490	2.1230890	3.1241410
C	3.5267250	-0.0383010	1.5287010
C	5.3233740	1.0954760	0.2336250
C	5.1574870	2.4533420	0.4882750
H	4.3699370	2.8086290	1.1349620
C	6.0397830	3.3477230	-0.1165490
H	5.8975990	4.4020450	0.0917940
C	7.0805550	2.9435960	-0.9645280
C	7.2272630	1.5750080	-1.2051080
H	8.0183350	1.2098780	-1.8540390
C	6.3612170	0.6627830	-0.6148770
C	6.2899650	-0.7790030	-0.6915730
C	7.0694700	-1.7024190	-1.3858600
H	7.8913920	-1.3434710	-1.9953810
C	6.7886320	-3.0632700	-1.2921280
C	5.7058090	-3.4529620	-0.4830260
H	5.4646190	-4.5081000	-0.3921740
C	4.9131600	-2.5528780	0.2191610
H	4.0919350	-2.8963680	0.8294000
C	5.2137660	-1.1950740	0.1105000
C	8.0422140	3.9336870	-1.6219970
C	7.7317180	5.3829840	-1.2440070
H	6.7266330	5.6792370	-1.5615120
H	7.8155310	5.5481880	-0.1649190
H	8.4457090	6.0490430	-1.7382870
C	7.9402930	3.8002600	-3.1490160
H	6.9256050	4.0260730	-3.4925170
H	8.6296770	4.4985130	-3.6359990
H	8.1936490	2.7904490	-3.4851580

C	9.4780270	3.6157280	-1.1776970
H	10.1812200	4.3133970	-1.6453890
H	9.5782560	3.7060150	-0.0912580
H	9.7745860	2.6014970	-1.4610920
C	7.6044350	-4.1263470	-2.0263890
C	8.2209210	-5.0904950	-1.0015550
H	8.8053150	-5.8624760	-1.5138830
H	8.8867880	-4.5559740	-0.3163870
H	7.4538840	-5.5924880	-0.4045840
C	6.6826620	-4.9093510	-2.9736010
H	7.2532370	-5.6795430	-3.5038730
H	5.8725890	-5.4065430	-2.4319960
H	6.2334500	-4.2436120	-3.7176110
C	8.7364150	-3.5141410	-2.8530140
H	9.2910670	-4.3105310	-3.3586730
H	8.3552940	-2.8345470	-3.6223070
H	9.4444210	-2.9628360	-2.2255660
O	-0.0218730	-1.2756770	4.9233410
N	-2.9930220	1.2271420	1.8545010
N	-3.0958800	-1.1570190	1.9619310
N	-4.6109810	0.0460960	0.6854660
C	-1.9393500	1.2111280	2.6526010
H	-1.5101820	2.1717180	2.9287560
C	-1.4021030	0.0195660	3.1371880
C	-2.0413610	-1.1593250	2.7593610
H	-1.6933230	-2.1228730	3.1242380
C	-3.5267220	0.0384240	1.5287000
C	-5.3233340	-1.0954500	0.2336670
C	-5.1573980	-2.4533000	0.4883660
H	-4.3698350	-2.8085360	1.1350660
C	-6.0396620	-3.3477340	-0.1164260
H	-5.8974400	-4.4020440	0.0919540
C	-7.0804490	-2.9436740	-0.9644190
C	-7.2272070	-1.5751000	-1.2050470
H	-8.0182910	-1.2100210	-1.8539910
C	-6.3611920	-0.6628230	-0.6148490
C	-6.2899890	0.7789620	-0.6915980
C	-7.0695280	1.7023260	-1.3859180
H	-7.8914380	1.3433260	-1.9954240
C	-6.7887380	3.0631900	-1.2922340

C	-5.7059290	3.4529490	-0.4831470
H	-5.4647770	4.5080990	-0.3923320
C	-4.9132460	2.5529190	0.2190710
H	-4.0920330	2.8964600	0.8292960
C	-5.2138030	1.1950990	0.1104590
C	-8.0420740	-3.9338230	-1.6218500
C	-7.7315250	-5.3830960	-1.2438080
H	-6.7264300	-5.6793240	-1.5613040
H	-7.8153320	-5.5482630	-0.1647150
H	-8.4454940	-6.0491980	-1.7380630
C	-7.9401600	-3.8004480	-3.1488750
H	-6.9254650	-4.0262360	-3.4923680
H	-8.6295190	-4.4987430	-3.6358310
H	-8.1935540	-2.7906580	-3.4850520
C	-9.4778980	-3.6158990	-1.1775600
H	-10.1810670	-4.3136110	-1.6452250
H	-9.5781220	-3.7061500	-0.0911180
H	-9.7744930	-2.6016890	-1.4609910
C	-7.6045800	4.1262110	-2.0265340
C	-8.2210930	5.0903790	-1.0017350
H	-8.8055160	5.8623210	-1.5140920
H	-8.8869400	4.5558630	-0.3165430
H	-7.4540710	5.5924220	-0.4047870
C	-6.6828370	4.9092090	-2.9737810
H	-7.2534400	5.6793590	-3.5040820
H	-5.8727790	5.4064490	-2.4321990
H	-6.2336050	4.2434550	-3.7177660
C	-8.7365430	3.5139350	-2.8531300
H	-9.2912210	4.3102870	-3.3588210
H	-8.3554020	2.8343210	-3.6223960
H	-9.4445300	2.9626340	-2.2256570

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